

777 EMPENNAGE CERTIFICATION APPROACH

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SUMMARY: This paper presents the Boeing approach to certification of the 777 composite empennage structure. The design team used carbon-fiber-reinforced plastic (CFRP) materials for the horizontal and vertical stabilizers, the elevators, and the rudder of the new 777 twinjet. Boeing based its approach to certification on analysis supported by coupon and component test evidence in compliance with guidelines issued by the FAA and JAA. The test program validated analysis methods, material design values, and manufacturing processes. The new toughened resin material used on the 777 provides improved damage resistance over conventional thermoset materials. The 777 empennage represents a major commitment to composites in commercial aircraft service.

KEYWORDS: commercial transport aircraft, certification, structural testing, carbon-fiber reinforced plastic **Error! Bookmark not defined.**, composite structure, strength, damage tolerance, and fatigue.

INTRODUCTION

Many components on the 777 aircraft contain composite materials (figure 1). Examples include fairings, floorbeams, engine nacelles, movable and fixed wing trailing edge surfaces, gear doors, and the empennage-including the horizontal and vertical stabilizers, elevators, and rudder. Composite materials are used primarily to reduce weight and improve aircraft efficiency. For some components, composite materials are appropriate, based on other requirements such as fatigue resistance, surface complexity, corrosion resistance, or manufacturing preference.

The use of CFRP in 777 empennage structure follows developmental work and commercial service from the early 1980s. The NASA/Boeing 737 horizontal stabilizer was the first major component of composite structure certified for commercial use [1]. The company introduced five shipsets into service in 1984. The approach taken by Boeing to obtain certification and acceptance by the FAA was a key milestone in the development of composite structure for commercial aircraft applications. This certification approach complies with FAA and JAA regulations and maintains the Boeing philosophy that aircraft structure certification is shown by analysis with supporting test evidence.

Following the 737 horizontal stabilizer program, Boeing designed a composite empennage for the 7J7 airplane. Although the company did not commit this model to production, Fuji Heavy Industries (FHI) fabricated a full-scale horizontal stabiliser test article (figure 2). Japan

Aircraft Development Corporation (JADC) performed static, fatigue, and damage tolerance testing of the stabilizer test article [2].

The 7J7 empennage represented the first significant use of a toughened-resin CFRP material. The test program complied with applicable regulations and addressed items outlined in the certification agency advisory circulars for composite aircraft structures [3]. The full-scale test, along with a comprehensive ancillary test program, met all of the advisory circular recommendations. It provided full-scale validation of the design and analysis methodology, fabrication processes, and damage tolerance capability of toughened-resin materials.

Boeing has expanded the use of composite materials to other applications. The Boeing 737, 747, 757, and 767 aircraft use composite materials in wing fixed leading and trailing edge structure and control surfaces. The rudder, elevator, aileron, and spoilers on these models use CFRP sandwich construction.

Figure 1: Composite Materials Usage on the 777

The use of composite materials on the 777 horizontal and vertical stabilizers originated as part of a company-funded program. Boeing built a prototype or preproduction composite horizontal stabiliser, based on the 767-200 planform (figure 3). Designers selected the 767-200 as a base configuration with known weight, loads, cost, and structural characteristics. The 777 preproduction horizontal stabilizer design evolved with long-term production in mind; a major objective was to validate manufacturing costs. Other objectives for the program included:

- Use composites where weight reduction can be achieved at a reasonable cost.
- Use toughened-resin materials or additional gage to increase resistance to service threats.
- Provide for a wide range of repair options, including mechanically fastened repairs.
- Provide access for maintenance, inspections, and repair.

- Design for visual in-service inspections only.
- Design to maximize automated fabrication processes.

Because of the similarity in structure, geometry, and materials, the FAA and JAA accepted the preproduction stabilizer and supporting test program as applicable experience and part of the certification basis for the 777 empennage. Full-scale testing of production aircraft structure, including the empennage components, is complete. This, together with other test data, forms the basis by which joint FAA/JAA certification has been granted. The 777-200 is in production and operating in service with the first eight customers.

Fig. 2: 777 CFRP Horizontal Stabilizer Test Article

Figure 3: Configuration of the Preproduction Horizontal Stabilizer

DESCRIPTION OF STRUCTURE

The 777 empennage consists of the horizontal and vertical stabilisers, elevators, and rudder (figure 4). The design team configured each stabilizer as a two-cell box, consisting of a main structural box and an auxiliary or forward torque box, leading edges, tip, and fixed trailing edges. The main torque boxes are made from CFRP composite material: solid-laminate front and rear spars, honeycomb sandwich ribs, and integrally stiffened laminate skin panels.

The main box panels and spars feature a toughened-matrix CFRP material from Toray. The preimpregnated fiber/resin system is T800/3900-2. It provides improved resistance to impact damage over previous brittle materials. The auxiliary torque box and fixed trailing edges are glass or glass/CFRP sandwich panels with aluminum ribs. The leading edge, tip, and auxiliary spar are aluminum construction. The Boeing Company manufactures both stabilisers at the Composite Manufacturing Center near Tacoma, Washington.

The elevator and rudder are also constructed from CFRP sandwich panels, ribs, and spars and are hinged from the stabiliser or fin fixed trailing edge. The rudder incorporates a lower tab of CFRP sandwich construction. ASTA fabricates the rudder in Australia; Hawker de Havilland fabricates the elevators. Reference 4 contains a more detailed description of the 777 empennage components.

CERTIFICATION APPROACH

This section describes the certification approach, together with the regulations and means of compliance. Topics include internal loads, environment, static strength, damage tolerance, and fatigue.

FAR Part 25 and JAR Part 25 [5, 6] define the regulatory requirements applicable to the 777 aircraft. Table I summarizes the principal requirements for structural strength, design, and construction. In addition to the regulations, the FAA and JAA have identified an acceptable means of compliance for certification of composite structure [3].

*Figure 4: 777-200 Empennage
(cover panels not shown)*

The advisory circular includes requirements in the following areas: (1) effects of environment (including design allowables and impact damage); (2) static strength (including repeated loads, test environment, process control, material variability, and impact damage); (3) fatigue and damage tolerance evaluation; and (4, other items such as flutter, flammability, lightning protection, maintenance, and repair.

The 777 empennage certification approach is primarily analytical, supported by test evidence at the coupon, element, subcomponent, and component levels and full-scale limit load test at ambient environment. The environmental effects on the composite structure are characterised at the coupon, element, and subcomponent levels and are accounted for in the structural analysis. Supporting evidence includes testing through a "building-block" approach that obtains material characterisation, allowables and analysis methods development, design concept verification, and final proof of structure (figure 5).

Experience with similar structure was important in developing the 777 certification program. The 7J7 horizontal stabilizer [2, 7] and the 777 preproduction horizontal stabilizer programs validated analytical methods, design allowab[les], and fabrication and assembly processes applied to the 777 empennage structure. Boeing has accumulated significant additional

knowledge and experience in characterising the behavior of composite aircraft structure. Boeing has augmented this experience database with the 737 composite stabilizer fleet experience and numerous other production applications in control surfaces, fixed secondary structure, fairings, and doors.

*Table 1: Regulations
Concerning Composite Structure Certification*

Topic	Reg	Subject
Material and process specifications	25.603 25.605	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control of materials • Fabrication methods
Material properties	25.613 25.615 25.619	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material strength properties and design values • Design properties • Special factors
Proof strength	25.305 25.307	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strength and deformation • Proof of structure
Damage tolerance	25.571	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fatigue evaluation • Residual strength • Discrete source damage
Other	25.581 25.609	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lightning protection • Protection of structure

The FAA and JAA participated in the certification approach for the 777. They participated directly through discussion and approval of the certification plan and indirectly through Boeing designated engineering representatives (DER). FAA representatives witnessed nearly all significant subcomponent and full-scale production component tests.

Internal Loads

Load models (figure 6) based on finite element analysis (FEA) determine internal load distributions. Elevators and the rudder are part of the model and attach to the main structure with the control surface position corresponding to the load condition being analyzed. External loads representing airplane aerodynamic and inertia loads are applied as nodal loads to the entire FEA model of each respective stabiliser and control surface. The FEA model determines hygrothermal loads for superposition with mechanical loads. The horizontal stabilizer model is a stand-alone analysis; the vertical stabilizer includes the interaction effects with the fuselage as a boundary condition at the fin base, obtained from the airplane major finite element model.

Figure 5: Building Block Approach for Design and Environmental Accountability

Design Environments

Analyses determined the most critical environment expected in airline service. In areas away from local heat sources, the thermal analysis predicts a maximum in-flight temperature of 71 CC (I 60°F) and a minimum temperature of -54°C (-65°F). Engineers studied the effect of moisture on the material systems applied in the empennage. They determined that it is highly unlikely that a moisture content of 1.1% by weight will be exceeded in service.

Figure 6: Finite Element Model, 777 Empennage Structure

Static Strength

The substantiation of static strength began by establishing material properties and design values utilizing coupon, element, and subcomponent data. Concurrently, engineers established methods of analysis. Stress analysis follows in which the design is analyzed using ground, flight, and inertia loads accounting for the configuration, dimensions, and properties of the structure. The analyses employ a variety of semiempirical methods, continuum mechanics, and special finite element solutions. The resulting calculated strains are compared to design values to show positive margins of safety for all critical load conditions. Strain surveys and limit load testing on the full-scale airplane confirm the accuracy of the internal loads model and analysis. Testing of elements, subcomponents, and the preproduction stabilizer provides additional evidence with ultimate load and repeated load data, including damage and environment.

A test program provided laminate-level allowable design strain values covering each failure mode and environmental condition. Corrections for material variability followed approved procedures in MIL-Handbook 17 [8]. The testing covered laminate configurations typical of the 777 empennage structure. Representative subcomponent tests accounting for the effects of environment verified detail design values.

Laminated composites are susceptible to the effects of impact damage. The 777 empennage design recognizes this by using toughened-resin CFRP materials and by limiting design strains. Subcomponent tests to establish design strains include the presence of impact damage. As a result, the composite structure design is capable of sustaining ultimate load with isolated impact damage, inflicted by any likely energy source, that cannot be detected visually. This type of damage is frequently referred to as "barely visible impact damage." Visibility studies

using a range of damages applied to several components determined the threshold of detectability.

Damage Tolerance and Fatigue

FAR and JAR 25.571 [5, 6] and the advisory circulars [3] describe two primary damage tolerance requirements: damage growth characterisation and residual strength capability. As in the case of static strength, damage tolerance certification is based on analysis supported by tests at element, subcomponent, and component levels. Considering the applied strains, Boeing selected a no-growth approach for the 777 empennage similar to that used for the 737 program [9]. This philosophy states that any damage that is visually undetectable is not critical. Structures with this type of damage must be capable of carrying ultimate load for the operational life of the airplane.

No-growth behavior was exhibited in numerous subcomponent tests and two full-scale cyclic load tests: the 7J7 horizontal stabilizer [7] and the preproduction 777 horizontal stabiliser. In each case, visible damage was inflicted on the test article that underwent spectrum type repeated loading. Nondestructive test personnel inspected damage sites for growth during the test sequence. Full-scale tests have further demonstrated the following characteristics:

- Manufacturing anomalies allowed per the process specifications will not grow for the equivalent of more than two design service lives.
- Visible damage due to foreign-object impact will not grow for the duration of two inspection intervals.
- The structure can sustain specified residual strength loads with damage that can reasonably be expected in service.
- The structure can sustain specified static loads ("continued safe flight loads") after incurring in-flight discrete-source damage.

In the case of fatigue, the 777 structure design meets or exceeds the safety and economic maintenance standards of current commercial transport aircraft. The design service life goal is the equivalent of 40,000 flights of 1.5 hours' duration, 25,000 flights of 3 hours' duration, or 10,000 flights of 9 hours' duration, whichever is critical.

Boeing based fatigue evaluation of the metal structure on established methods. Tests have characterised the fatigue behavior of the composite structure at coupon, element, and subcomponent levels, as well as in full-scale tests. The full-scale component tests have verified that deliberately inflicted damage does not grow under operating loads.

The 777 structural inspection plan will prevent catastrophic failure during the operational life of the airframe by detecting fatigue, corrosion, or accidental damage. Boeing has established an initial structural inspection and maintenance plan, based on the procedures of the Airline/Manufacturer Maintenance Planning document. This approach analyzes the airplane structure in terms of environmental and accidental damage potential with consideration for material, location, inspectability, and past service experience.

DEVELOPMENT TEST PROGRAM

The test program developed to support analysis and certification for the 777 empennage was part of an overall approach reviewed with the regulatory authorities. This section reviews tests and results, together with their place in the compliance plan: 777 preproduction stabiliser, vertical stabilizer root attachment, elements, and subcomponents.

777 Preproduction Horizontal Stabilizer Test

The 777 preproduction horizontal stabiliser test article was nearly identical to the production component. The test article was a partial span box. Designers eliminated the minimum gage outboard sections for cost considerations and replaced them with load application fixtures. The test article included typical, specification-allowed process anomalies, as well as low-velocity impact damage up to and beyond the visual threshold. Figure 7 shows the test article; figure 8 shows the test load sequence. Reference 4 contains more detailed description, including the test setup.

Figure 7: Preproduction Horizontal Stabilizer Test

One of the test objectives was to validate the "no-growth" design philosophy for damage [3]. To do this, impact damages were inflicted on the test box at the barely visible level. Boeing conducted fatigue testing for load cycles representative of two design service lifetimes. Periodic ultrasonic inspection revealed an absence of detrimental damage growth. This test included a 1.5S load enhancement factor to account for possible fatigue scatter associated with the flat S-N curves typical of composite materials.

Limit load strain surveys and initial ultimate load testing results demonstrated the predictive capability of the FEA internal loads model. Measured strains were at or below predicted strains. There was no indication of permanent deformation in any component.

To demonstrate residual strength capability the test box was further damaged with visible impacts. Visible damages are those that are easily detected by scheduled maintenance inspections. Fatigue testing representative of two inspection intervals again verified the

no-growth approach. Limit load testing verified that the structure was capable of carrying the required loads (FAR 25.571b) with these damages existing in the structure.

Engineers then inflicted the test box with major damage in the form of saw cuts to the front and rear spar chords and a completely severed stringer/skin segment. Testing demonstrated the capability to sustain continued safe-flight loads (FAR 25.571e). Again, ultrasonic inspection of the deliberately inflicted damages showed no detrimental growth. Residual strength testing substantiated the analytical predictions and empirical results based on subcomponent test characterisation.

Upon completion of the damage tolerance testing, mechanics repaired the cut element damages and the major through-penetration impact damages, using bolted titanium sheet metal repairs. Mechanics made the repairs using external access only, simulating in-service repair conditions. The test article demonstrated design ultimate load (DUL) capability with the repairs in place.

The test article was loaded to destruction using a symmetric down bending load case. A two-piece rupture occurred in the lower surface skin panel between ribs one and two. Final failure occurred above the required load level. Engineers predicted the skin panel failure using the analytical methods and design values derived from five stringer compression panel subcomponent tests.

Fig. 8: Preproduction horizontal stabilizer test sequence

In summary, the preproduction stabiliser test substantiated the following findings:

- The "no-damage growth" behavior.
- The strength, durability, and damage tolerance of the 777 CFRP empennage design.

- The methods of analysis, material properties, and design values used to design and analyze a CFRP empennage.
- The capability of the ELFINI internal loads model for predicting strain distributions and deflections.
- The design and application of mechanically fastened repairs.

Vertical Stabilizer Root Attachment Test

Boeing conducted two large subcomponent tests to evaluate the primary joint of the 777 vertical stabiliser root attachment to the fuselage. The main objective of the tests was to

validate the analysis and load distribution assumptions for the joint. These tests also satisfied requests by the FAA and JAA for demonstrating ultimate load capability (FAR/JAR 25.305 and 25.307) and durability (FAR/JAR 25.571) of this CFRP/titanium joint.

The program achieved these objectives by fabricating two test articles representative of the 777-200 design, each composed of a four-bay section of CFRP skin panel and rear spar chord with two titanium root fittings (see figure 9). The first article was subjected to static testing in a series of limit and ultimate load conditions in tension and compression, culminating in a destruction test under tension loads. The final tension test loaded the article to 1.5 times DUL when the shear fasteners at the stabilizer-to-body interface failed. The skin and fittings remained intact as did the tension bolt/barrel nut connection.

The objective of the fatigue test was to find potential fatigue critical areas and investigate crack growth behavior. The second test article was tested with cyclic loads at a constant amplitude followed by a tensile residual strength test. Cracks in titanium clips and fittings developed.

Figure 9: 777 Vertical Fin Root Joint Test Article

Post-test inspection of the cracks showed that the most detrimental crack began well after two equivalent design service lifetimes. The fatigue test was followed by residual strength tests in compression to limit load and in tension to failure. The panel failed under tension loading at approximately 1.5 times DUL, caused initially by the failure of the shear fasteners at the stabilizer-to-body interface, followed by a two-piece failure in the CFRP skin panel.

Subcomponent Tests

Subcomponent tests established point design values and validated methods of analysis for skin panel, spar, rib, trailing edge beam, and horizontal stabiliser centerline splice joint. These design values accounted for the effects of environment, the presence of barely visible impact damage, and for large damages. The Subcomponent test results comprise a significant portion of the test evidence required to validate analytical methods and demonstrate the required levels of static strength and damage tolerance for the 777 empennage.

Subcomponent test results validated the following critical design values and methods of analysis:

- Compression ultimate strength design value curve for stiffened skin panels.
- Shear-compression ultimate strength interaction curve for stiffened skin panels.
- Compression and tension damage tolerance analysis for stiffened skin panels.
- Strength of bolted and bonded repair designs for stiffened skin panels.
- Bolted joint analysis and design values for the skin panel-to-trailing edge rib joints.
- Static compression strength, tension strength, and tension fatigue performance of the horizontal stabilizer centerline splice joint.
- Analytical methods for spar strain distributions, web stability, and peak strains at cutouts.
- Analytical methods for rib shear tie and chord strength and stiffness.
- Peak strain design values for rib shear tie cutouts.

Figure 10a: Typical Bolted Repair on CFRP Skin Panel Test, Interior View

Several test types demonstrated no-growth of small damages under operational repeated loading. These tests complemented the results from the full-scale component fatigue testing and involved the following articles:

- Axially loaded flat panels.
- Shear loaded flat panels with cutouts.
- Stiffened panel with a bonded repair.
- Spar shear beams with web cutouts.
- Centerline splice joint stiffened panel.

Figure 10b: Typical Bolted Repair on CFRP Skin Panel Test, Exterior View

A major focus of the empennage subcomponent test program involved the main torque box skin panels. These panels consist of an integrally stiffened solid laminate skin with I-section stringers. A series of] O five-stringer, three-rib-bay compression panels with small impact damages established the panel] design strain curve. Engineers derived the design strain values from the panel failure loads, using a modification of the classical effective width analysis technique. Tests were conducted at room temperature and hot/wet conditions and included barely visible impact damage and typical manufacturing flaws.

Tests on eight five-stringer panels validated repair concepts. Three tests contained bolted repairs using titanium doubler plates (figure 10); five tests contained bonded prepreg scarf joint repairs. All panels demonstrated ultimate load capability. Six of the panels were tested in compression; one panel of each repair type was tested in tension. Two bonded repair compression panels were tested in a hot/wet condition.

The bonded repair tension panel contained impact damages and was fatigue cycled for two lifetimes of operational loads without damage growth or disbond of the repair. Figure 11 shows a compression panel with a bonded repair under load; the moiré image clearly shows the buckle pattern of the skin panel and the location of the repair.

Tests on another 10 five-stringer compression panels and two five-stringer tension panels demonstrated capability for various large damages. Damage configurations included disbanded stringers, clearly visible impact damages, and saw cut damages to the skin and to a skin/stringer element. The first two damage types validated capability for regulatory fail-safe (FAR 25.571b) damage tolerance evaluations, while the saw cut damages validated capability for discrete source (FAR 25.571e) evaluations.

Tests on five-stringer panels loaded in combined shear and compression validated the shear-compression design envelope. Six panels with small damages were tested in a specialized test machine at several shear/compression load ratios. Engineers conducted additional stiffened panel tests to validate specific design details, including stringer runouts, the stabilizer centerline splice joint, and trailing edge rib-to-skin joints.

Figure 11:
Bonded Repair on CFRP Skin Panel Test

Subcomponent tests for the main torque box spars and ribs focused primarily on validating ultimate strength capability of these items. These tests included impact damages and environmental effects.

In summary, the subcomponent testing provided data to support the development of specific design values and to validate analytical methods. These design values and methods supported findings of compliance for FARs 25.307, 25.571, 25.603, 25.605, and 25.613. Engineers developed this supporting data using procedures that follow the guidelines in the composite structure advisory circulars [3].

Coupon and Element Tests

Boeing conducted an extensive coupon and element level test program in support of new 777 composite structure applications. These tests established material stiffness properties,

statistical allowables, and strength design values and validated analytical methods. Tests also established laminate level statistical allowables for unnotched and notched conditions, following recommended procedures [8].

Table 2: Summary of T800/3900-2 CFRP Material Coupon and Element Tests

Test Type	Number of Tests
Ply properties	235
Long-term environmental exposure	200
Laminate strength	2,334
Interlaminar strength	574
Radius details	184
Crippling	271
Stress concentrations	118
Effects of defects	494
Bolted joints	3,025
Durability	385
Bonded repair	239
Total	8,059

Testing covered laminate, joint, and structural configurations typical of the 777 empennage; temperatures from -54°C to 82°C; moisture conditioned laminates; and the effects of

manufacturing variations and anomalies allowed within the process specifications. A limited amount of impact damage testing was performed at the element level. Test article configurations ranged from simple rectangular coupons to bolted joint, angle-section, I-section, and shear panel element tests. Table 2 shows a summary of the testing.

PRODUCTION COMPONENT TESTS

The following section discusses the full-scale production component tests for the 777 horizontal and vertical stabilisers. The primary objective of this testing is limit load substantiation in compliance with FAR/JAR 25.305 and 25.307. A further objective is to verify the load distribution and analytical methodology. Previous experience from ultimate load and failure testing of the 737, 7J7, and 777 preproduction horizontal stabiliser test boxes removed the need to test the 777 production structure beyond limit load for certification

Figure 12: 777 Horizontal Stabilizer Test Setup

777 Horizontal Stabilizer Tests

Boeing tested the 777 horizontal stabiliser and elevators separately from the airplane because the attachment to the body is determinate. The test specimen was a structurally complete production article (figure 12). The test plan omitted nonstructural components and systems not essential to the structural performance or induced loading of the stabiliser.

The strakelet and tip Airings were not installed, and the elevator actuators were replaced by rigid links. The test specimen was fabricated by the same construction methods and governed by the same specification requirements as other production structure. Inspectors maintained FAA conformity on a majority of the parts during fabrication. Tests began in April 1994 and were complete in June of 1995.

Figure 13: 777 Horizontal Stabilizer Test Sequence

Figure 14: 777 Horizontal Stabilizer Test, Predicted Versus Actual Strains

Engineers computed test loads for each static load condition to match the required shear, moment, and torsion values. These test loads were applied to the stabiliser using hydraulic actuators connected to attachment fittings, mounted on the stabiliser structure. The stabilizer was mounted in the test fixture at the pivot and jackscrew fittings, as it would be in an airplane. The test article was instrumented with strain gages, electronic deflection indicators (EDI), and calibrated load-cells at selected locations. Instrumentation monitored structural

responses and provided data for correlation to analytical predictions during all strain surveys. Testing was conducted outdoors at ambient conditions.

The test included three critical static load conditions: up, down, and unsymmetric bending. Figure 13 depicts the loading sequence. As in the preproduction test box, limit load strain survey results demonstrated the predictive capability of the PEA model. Calculations accurately predicted measured strains (figure 14). Overall deflection along the span of the stabilizer correlated well (figure 15). There were no signs of permanent deformation.

Figure 15: 777 Horizontal Stabilizer Test, Predicted Versus Actual Deflection

Additional testing that was not required for certification included fatigue, ultimate load, and destruct testing. The horizontal stabilizer was subjected to 120,000 flights of spectrum fatigue loading to satisfy the program objectives. This test verified the fatigue characteristics of the metallic portion of the stabilizer. The preproduction test box described earlier verified the composite structure.

Ultimate load and destruct testing supplemented the data that was acquired as part of the certification program. The test team ran three load cases representative of up, down, and unsymmetric bending. The critical down bending load case became the destruct run. The test box was subjected to barely visible impact damage and loaded to failure. Engineers accurately identified the failure location and predicted the failure load within 3D. Final failure occurred above the required load level.

The 777 horizontal stabilizer test program met the following goals:

- Verified compliance with FAR/JAR 25.305 and 25.307. The test article sustained limit load for critical conditions without permanent deformation.
- Verified predictive capability of analysis methods coupled with subcomponent tests. Strains and deflections closely matched the analysis.
- Verified the design service goals of the 777 horizontal stabilizer.
- Verified the absence of widespread damage due to fatigue.

777 Vertical Stabilizer Test

Boeing tested the 777 vertical stabilizer, including the rudder, as part of the airplane fullscale test (figure 16). Again, the purpose was to show limit load capability and verify the accuracy of analytically calculated strains and deflections. Tests began in June of 1994 as part of the

fullscale airplane test and were completed in April of 1995. Boeing used a second airplane with vertical stabilizer and rudder in the major fatigue test, which began in January of 1995.

Figure 16: 777 Vertical Stabilizer Test Setup

The static test article was the second production airplane built. The aft portion of the aircraft was structurally complete except for nonstructural components and systems; the horizontal stabilizer was replaced by a load fixture attached at the pivot bulkhead and jackscrew attachment. The leading edge and tip were not installed on the vertical stabilizer, and the rudder actuators were replaced by rigid links.

Figure 17: 777 Vertical Stabilizer Test, Predicted Versus Actual Strains

As described for the horizontal stabilizer test, engineers computed loads for critical cases, based on the external load conditions, and applied them through a series of actuators, fixtures, and pads. The test article contained a full set of instrumentation to monitor behavior and collect data for comparison with the analysis. Testing was conducted indoors at ambient conditions.

Three critical conditions tested included maximum bending (engine-out), maximum torsion (hinge moment), and maximum shear (lateral gust). Technicians applied other test conditions as part of the overall airplane test sequence, which were not critical for the vertical stabiliser. In comparison with the analysis, measured strains were accurately predicted (figure 17). Measured deflection along the span of the fin correlated well with the FEA loads model (figure 18). There were no signs of permanent deformation.

A completely separate test using another production airframe verified the fatigue behavior of the 777. This test subjected the vertical stabiliser and rudder to 120,000 flights of spectrum fatigue loading. The 777 vertical stabiliser test program exceeded the same goals as described for the horizontal stabiliser test.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the 777 empennage certification program have provided data to show compliance with FAA and JAA regulations. The results also add to confidence in the use of composite materials in large primary structures for commercial transport aircraft. The necessary steps leading to this conclusion entail: (1) an early certification plan developed by working together with the FAA and JAA; (2) a dedicated material characterisation program:

Figure 18: 777 Vertical Stabilizer Test, Predicted Versus Actual Deflection

(3) substantiation of static strength by analysis, accounting for the effects of damage and environment, and the supporting static tests; and (4) damage tolerance verification with a no-growth approach and the supporting test data. On each major item, Boeing has complied

with the guidelines established by the regulatory authorities. The resultant composite airplane components are safe and reliable.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the many and diverse contributions of the 777 empennage design-build team and support staff. We also acknowledge David R. Wilson, Karl H. Schreiber, and John T. Quinlivan for their leadership in the 777 certification process. We are thankful to Stan Wood of the FAA for his oversight during the course of the program. Thanks to Peter J. Smith for his encouragement. The authors remember Ernie Dost, who always wanted to work on the 777 empennage, but instead worked to broaden our smiles and further our knowledge of impact damage resistance.

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